

Bridging Tradition and Science: Evidence-Based Unani Regimenal Therapies in Gastrointestinal Disorders

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ABSTRACT

Background: Gastrointestinal (GI) disorders are among the most prevalent health conditions worldwide and are commonly associated with impaired digestion, altered bowel motility, inflammation, and reduced quality of life. Although modern gastroenterology offers effective pharmacological options, long-term use is often limited by adverse effects, symptom recurrence, and economic burden. Traditional systems such as Unani medicine emphasize regimenal therapies (Ilaj-bit-Tadbeer) to restore digestive balance and humoral equilibrium. **Objectives:** To review classical Unani concepts of digestion and gastrointestinal pathology and critically evaluate contemporary scientific evidence supporting major Unani regimenal therapies—Fasd (venesection), Hammam (therapeutic bath), Ta'liq al-'Alaq (leech therapy), and Huqna (medicated enema)—in gastrointestinal disorders. **Methods:** This narrative review analyzed classical Unani texts, including Al-Qanun fi al-Tibb and Al-Mukhtarat Fit Tib, to extract traditional concepts, indications, and therapeutic rationale. A literature search of PubMed, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect was conducted to identify contemporary clinical and experimental studies evaluating physiological mechanisms and clinical outcomes of these regimenal therapies. **Results:** Evidence indicates that venesection improves hepatic and metabolic parameters through iron reduction and decreased oxidative stress; hammam and heat-based therapies enhance bowel motility, metabolic regulation, and gut–brain peptide release; leech therapy demonstrates anti-inflammatory, anticoagulant, and hepatoprotective effects; and enemas provide effective relief in constipation, bowel urgency, and inflammatory bowel disease, improving quality of life. **Conclusion:** Integrating evidence-based Unani regimenal therapies with contemporary gastroenterology offers a holistic, safe, and cost-effective approach for managing gastrointestinal disorders.

Keywords: Unani medicine; Ilaj-bit-Tadbeer; gastrointestinal disorders; Fasd; Hammam; leech therapy; Huqna; integrative gastroenterology

INTRODUCTION

Gastrointestinal (GI) disorders constitute a major global health concern, affecting 2.5 billion people globally and significantly impairing quality of life. These disorders commonly arise from disturbances in digestive function, dietary and lifestyle factors, and altered gastrointestinal motility, often manifesting as chronic symptoms such as abdominal pain, bloating, constipation, and intestinal inflammation. Despite notable advances in modern gastroenterology, conventional therapeutic approaches are frequently associated with adverse effects, recurrence of symptoms, and increased healthcare costs,

underscoring the need for complementary and integrative treatment strategies. The Unani system of medicine, rooted in Greco-Arab medical traditions, offers a comprehensive and holistic understanding of gastrointestinal health based on the principles of humoral theory and temperament (Mizaj). Classical Unani texts emphasize regimenal therapies (Ilaj-bit-Tadbeer) as a means to restore humoral equilibrium, eliminate morbid matter, and enhance physiological functions. Among these, Fasd (venesection), Hammam (therapeutic bath), Ta'liq al-'Alaq (leech therapy), and Huqna (medicated enema) have been traditionally employed in the prevention and management of various gastrointestinal disorders.

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In recent years, increasing scientific attention has been directed toward elucidating the physiological mechanisms and therapeutic outcomes associated with these traditional regimenal interventions. Available evidence suggests that these therapies may improve circulation, regulate bowel motility, facilitate detoxification, and reduce inflammatory processes, thereby contributing to gastrointestinal health. The integration of evidence-based traditional practices with contemporary gastroenterology may provide safe, cost-effective, and holistic approaches for the management of gastrointestinal disorders. (1) Accordingly, the present review aims to critically evaluate traditional Unani regimenal therapies and contemporary scientific evidence supporting their therapeutic role in gastrointestinal disorders.

METHODOLOGY

This narrative review was conducted using both classical Unani literature and contemporary scientific publications. Primary Unani sources, including *Al-Qanoon-fil-Tibb* and *Al Mukhtarat Fit Tib*, were reviewed to extract traditional concepts, indications, and therapeutic principles of regimenal therapies in gastrointestinal disorders. For contemporary evidence, an extensive literature search was performed using electronic databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect. The selected literature was critically analyzed to evaluate the physiological rationale, underlying mechanisms, and reported clinical outcomes associated with each regimenal therapy.

Concept Of Hazm, Humoral Balance, And Gastrointestinal Pathology In Unani Medicine

In Unani medicine, gastrointestinal health is fundamentally dependent on the integrity of Hazm (digestion), which is regarded as a multi-stage physiological process extending beyond the stomach to include hepatic, vascular, and tissue-level assimilation. The primary objective of Hazm is the conversion of ingested food into balanced *Akhlat* (humours), which serve as the nutritional and functional substrates for all bodily organs. Proper digestion ensures the formation of healthy humours, whereas impairment at any stage results in pathological states. The process of Hazm is governed by *Tabi'at* (innate regulating faculty) and facilitated

by *Quwa-e-Hazima* (digestive faculty) with the support of *Hararat-e-Ghariziyah* (innate heat). Classical Unani scholars like Ibn Sina(2) and Galen(3) describe four sequential stages of digestion—gastric (*haz'm-e- Ma'di*), hepatic (*ha'zm-e- Kabidi*), vascular (*Ha'zm-e-Urooqi*), and tissue digestion (*ha'zm-e-Uzwi*)—each contributing to progressive refinement of nutrients. Effective coordination among these stages is essential for maintaining gastrointestinal integrity and systemic health. The four humours—*Dam* (blood), *Balgham* (phlegm), *Safra* (yellow bile), and *Sauda* (black bile)—are produced primarily during *Hazm-e-Kabdi* (hepatic digestion) and play a pivotal role in gastrointestinal physiology. Each humour possesses specific qualities that influence digestive secretions, motility, absorption, and tissue nourishment.

Dam, being warm and moist, is primary nutritious humor formed post hepatic digestion, superior for tissue and energy(4).

Balgham, cold and moist, maintains lubrication and structural integrity of the gut.(4)

Safra, warm and dry, exerts a detergative action in the intestine by stimulating the enteric nervous system, enhancing gastrointestinal secretions and peristalsis, and facilitating fat digestion through emulsification.(5)

Sauda, cold and dry, provides structural firmness regulates organ tone act as appetizer.(6)

A balanced proportion of these humours ensures normal digestion and absorption, while any qualitative or quantitative disturbance predisposes to gastrointestinal dysfunction. *Su'-e-Mizaj* (derangement of temperament) is a central pathological concept in Unani medicine and is considered a primary cause of gastrointestinal disorders. *Su'-e-Mizaj* may affect the stomach, liver, intestines, or associated organs, leading to impaired digestive faculties and altered humoral production. It may occur with or without the accumulation of morbid matter (*Madda*). *Su'-e-Mizaj Hārr* results from excessive gastric heat causing accelerated chemical digestion, increased corrosive activity, and rapid gastric transit, whereas *Su'-e-Mizaj Bārid* is due to reduced innate heat leading to sluggish enzymatic

activity, delayed gastric emptying, and impaired transformation of food; *Su'-e-Mizāj Ratab* arises from excess moisture in the gastric environment causing dilution of digestive forces, incomplete food transformation, and increased luminal fluidity, while *Su'-e-Mizāj Yābis* is characterised by deficiency of gastric moisture resulting in impaired softening of ingested food, reduced lubrication, and delayed digestive processing.(7) When *hazm* (digestion) is disturbed, impaired digestive temperament leads to the formation of *akhlāt-e-fāsida*, resulting in burning or heaviness in the epigastrium, nausea, bloating, sour or foul belching, altered appetite and thirst, dryness or excessive moisture of the mouth, abnormal gastric transit, and bowel disturbances such as constipation or loose stools, varying with the predominance of *ḥarārat*, *burūdat*, *rutūbat*, or *yubūsat*.(7) Unani pathology emphasizes that gastrointestinal disorders are not isolated local conditions but reflect a broader systemic imbalance involving digestion, temperament, and humoral equilibrium. Therefore, effective management requires correction of *Hazm*, restoration of *Mizaj*, and elimination of morbid humours. Based on this integrated understanding, Unani medicine advocates regimenal interventions (*Ilaj-bit-Tadbeer*) aimed at strengthening digestive faculties, correcting *Su'-e-Mizaj*, and restoring humoral balance.

Regimenal Therapies In Gastrointestinal Disorders

Fasd (Venesection)

The term *Faṣd* literally denotes the act of incising or opening a blood vessel and refers to the deliberate cutting of a vein for therapeutic purposes (8). *Ibn-i-Habal al-Baghdadi* defined “venesection is a process of complete evacuation which drains blood and dominating humor mixed with blood from vein” (9). *Masihi* in the book *Al-'Umdah fil-Jarāḥat* characterized “*Faṣd* as an intentional form of *Tafarruq-i-Ittisāl* (disruption of continuity), produced in veins using specialized instruments for therapeutic benefit”(10). In broader medical terminology, venesection is also referred to as phlebotomy or bloodletting, a practice that has been employed as a therapeutic intervention by various medical traditions since antiquity and continues to hold relevance in

selected clinical contexts. In Unani medicine, *fasd* (venesection) has been historically prescribed for various liver disorders. While Unani texts prescribe *fasd* of cephalic and basilic vein for liver inflammation (*warm-e-kabid*) (11), modern studies validate its role in NAFLD through iron reduction, offering a non-pharmacological adjunct to lifestyle interventions.

Key Evidence

- A systematic review and meta-analysis of four interventional trials encompassing 438 patients demonstrated that therapeutic phlebotomy, aimed at reducing ferritin through repeated venesection, significantly ameliorated insulin resistance, decreased triglycerides, and raised HDL-C compared to lifestyle interventions alone. These metabolic and hepatoprotective effects resonate with Unani principles of *fasd* for evacuating excess blood in conditions of hepatic inflammation suggesting a mechanistic convergence via reduced oxidative stress and iron-mediated inflammation.(12)

Fasd (venesection) is an established therapeutic intervention for hepatic disorders characterized by *sudda* (obstruction) (9), abnormal hot temperament of the liver, and diseases such as hepatitis and jaundice, particularly when associated with excess or morbid blood (*ghalba-e-dam*). Classical Unani texts recommend venesection of specific veins, especially the basilic vein, to relieve hepatic congestion, restore humoral balance, and facilitate the resolution of obstruction (13). This traditional concept shows a meaningful correlation with modern gastroenterology, where therapeutic phlebotomy is the cornerstone of management in hemochromatosis—a condition marked by pathological iron overload leading to hepatic fibrosis, cirrhosis, and cholestatic manifestations, including jaundice. Regular venesection in hemochromatosis effectively reduces iron stores, decreases oxidative stress, and prevents progression of liver damage, thereby relieving functional hepatic obstruction at the microcellular level.(14,15). Thus, when viewed through an integrative lens, the Unani indication of *Fasd* in liver obstruction and jaundice parallels contemporary evidence supporting phlebotomy in

iron overload–related hepatic disorders, highlighting a shared pathophysiological rationale and reinforcing the relevance of Fasd in gastroenterological practice across traditional and modern systems of medicine.

Key Evidence

- A recent case report evaluated the hemodynamic effects and safety of repeated large-volume therapeutic phlebotomy in a 64-year-old patient with hemochromatosis undergoing nine sessions of 1000 mL venesection. The study demonstrated that acute blood removal was well tolerated, with mean arterial pressure maintained despite significant reductions in stroke volume and cardiac output, achieved through compensatory increases in heart rate and systemic vascular resistance. Even under added orthostatic stress, cardiovascular stability was preserved, indicating effective physiological adaptation to acute hypovolemia. These findings provide contemporary evidence that therapeutic phlebotomy is a safe and physiologically effective intervention in iron overload states, supporting its role in reducing blood viscosity and preventing organ damage, including hepatic complications associated with hemochromatosis (16).

Hammam (Therapeutic Bath)

The word Hammam is derived from the Arabic root *Hamm* which means “*spreader of warmth*” or that produces heat (17,18). According to *Ibne Sina* the word Hammam is derived from *Alhamim* which means the vehemence of summer heat. Hammam, also known as a Turkish bath or steam bath nowadays, is a traditional hydrotherapy practice originating from Roman, Byzantine, and Islamic cultures. It involves exposure to hot steam, often in a multi-room setup with varying temperatures and humidity levels, combined with scrubbing, massage, and sometimes herbal infusions. In traditional systems like Unani medicine (a Greco-Islamic medical tradition), hammam is classified as a regimental therapy (*Ilaj bil Tadbir*) aimed at balancing bodily humors, promoting detoxification, and enhancing overall health. Historically, medieval physicians such as *Ibn Hubal al-Baghdādī* (12th century) described hammam as beneficial for dissolving waste matter, liquefying bodily fluids, and expelling residues from the stomach

and intestines, thereby supporting digestion when timed appropriately (e.g., after initial food digestion to avoid obstruction)(19). This historical foundation has evolved into modern applications, where hammam is explored as a complementary therapy in gastroenterology for conditions involving digestion, motility, and metabolic disorders. In contemporary gastroenterology, hammam’s role is primarily investigative and adjunctive, drawing from its effects on circulation, stress reduction, and thermoregulation. While not a mainstream treatment, emerging evidence from integrative medicine suggests potential benefits for gastrointestinal (GI) disorders such as constipation, obesity-related liver issues, and general digestive motility. These effects are attributed to mechanisms like increased perspiration for toxin elimination, improved blood flow to the GI tract, and activation of heat shock proteins that may modulate inflammation and gut function.

Key Evidence:

- A single-arm, open-label clinical trial evaluated the efficacy of Hammām-i-yābis (dry bath) in 30 patients with metabolic syndrome and demonstrated significant improvements in systolic and diastolic blood pressure, waist circumference, fasting blood sugar, and serum triglyceride levels after 30 days of therapy. By improving central obesity, dyslipidemia, and insulin resistance—key components of metabolic syndrome that are closely linked with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, impaired digestion, and other gastrointestinal metabolic disorders—the study provides indirect but clinically relevant evidence for the role of Hammām-i-yābis in promoting GI health. The intervention was found to be safe, feasible, and effective, supporting its use as a non-pharmacological regimen for metabolic conditions with gastrointestinal involvement.(20)
- An open-label clinical trial showed that Riyazat combined with Hammām-e-Bukhari (steam bath) produced significant reductions in body weight, BMI, waist circumference, and skinfold thickness in patients with obesity, without adverse effects. By reducing central obesity and improving metabolic efficiency—key contributors to fatty

liver and other GI–metabolic disorders—the study supports the role of Hammām-e-Bukhari as an effective regimenal therapy for improving gastrointestinal-related metabolic health (21).

- Abdominal heat therapy, akin to localized hammam effects, has shown efficacy in elderly patients. A recent clinical study demonstrated that application of local abdominal heat significantly improved bowel function in elderly patients with constipation, with marked improvement in stool consistency observed on the first and second days of intervention compared to controls. The findings suggest that abdominal heat therapy enhances defecation and reduces constipation, supporting its use as a simple, safe, and effective complementary non-pharmacological intervention for gastrointestinal motility disorders (22).
- Heat exposure stimulates the release of brain-gut peptides. A study on sauna-induced hyperthermia (similar core temperature rise as in hammam) showed significant increases in plasma vasoactive intestinal polypeptide (VIP), pancreatic polypeptide (PP), and motilin during and after heat sessions. Motilin promotes intestinal contractions, aiding peristalsis, while PP and VIP regulate gastric emptying and relaxation of GI smooth muscle. This could alleviate slow transit in constipation or IBS-constipation predominant types (23).
- Passive heat therapies like saunas improve glucose tolerance and insulin signaling, potentially mitigating diabetes-related digestive complications(24)

Ta‘Liq Al-‘Alaq (Leech Therapy)

Leech therapy (Ta‘liq al-‘Alaq), a prominent regimenal intervention in the Unani system of medicine, is an ancient therapeutic modality rooted in the humoral theory, where disease is believed to arise from imbalance and accumulation of morbid humours. Among the various methods of Ilaj-bit-Tadbeer (regimenal therapy), leech therapy occupies a distinctive position as a localized and controlled form of bloodletting aimed at the evacuation of fasid akhlat from diseased tissues. Historically practiced for

over two millennia across diverse medical traditions including Unani, Ayurveda, Egyptian, Greek, and Arab medicine, leech therapy was extensively described by classical physicians such as Hippocrates, Galen, Ibn Sina, and Zakariya Razi, who emphasized its superiority in drawing blood from deeper and congested sites. Ancient physician used to treat chronic skin diseases, eye diseases, musculoskeletal diseases, gynaecological disorders, ENT disorders, thromboembolic diseases, local congestive condition, as well as brain congestion and mental illness. The commonest indications of Leech therapy as mentioned in Unani classics are *Jarabul Ajfaan* (Blephritis), *Dawali*(varicose vein), *Darde pindali* (Painful Calf muscle),*Malankholia* (Mania), *Qooruhe khabisa* (septic wound,non-healing ulcer), *Waram* (inflammation) of organs), *Khanaazeer* (Lymphadenitis), *Warme Tajaweful Anaf* (sinusitis), *Warme halq* (Pharyngitis), *Bawaseer* (Piles),*Nawaseer* (Fistula in ano), *Daa ul feel* (Elephantiasis), at the biting site of poisonous animals, skin disorders like *Qooba* (Ringworm), *Saafa* (Tinea corporis), *Namash* (Chloasma), *kalaf* (Warts), *Nar farsi* (eczema), *Daul sadaf* (psoriasis), *Bars* (Vitiligo), *Wajaul Mufasil* (Osteoarthritis) etc. (25,26)]In contemporary medicine, the re-emergence of leech therapy—termed hirudotherapy—has gained scientific recognition, particularly in plastic and reconstructive surgery, owing to its role in relieving venous congestion and enhancing microcirculation. The therapeutic efficacy of leech therapy is attributed to the bioactive constituents of leech saliva, including anticoagulant, anti-inflammatory, vasodilatory, analgesic, and thrombolytic agents. Accumulating clinical and experimental evidence supports its usefulness in managing conditions such as chronic wounds, varicose veins, osteoarthritis, hemorrhoids, and inflammatory disorders. This convergence of classical wisdom and modern evidence underscores the relevance of leech therapy as a viable complementary intervention in contemporary healthcare.

Key Evidence:

- A clinical study evaluating the efficacy of medicinal leech therapy (MLT) in patients with third- and fourth-degree hemorrhoids demonstrated significant symptomatic

improvement following treatment. Using the CORECTS scoring system, statistically significant reductions were observed in pain (44.09%), itching (38.55%), swelling (44%), bleeding (17.28%), and discomfort (34.01%), along with an improvement in overall wellbeing (32.35%), with most parameters showing p-values <0.001. Although the sample size was limited, the findings indicate that medicinal leech therapy is a safe and effective therapeutic option for reducing the severity of symptoms in advanced hemorrhoids, supporting its potential role as a complementary or alternative intervention in hemorrhoidal disease. (27)

- A case report describes the successful management of thrombosed hemorrhoids using leech therapy (Jaloukavacharana). A 39-year-old male presented with severe anal pain, burning sensation, mass per rectum, and intermittent bleeding. The patient was treated with multiple sittings of leech application on alternate days. Following therapy, there was marked reduction in pain, burning sensation, bleeding, and size of the thrombosed pile mass, with complete symptomatic relief and no recurrence or complications reported. The authors attributed the therapeutic benefit to the anticoagulant, thrombolytic, anti-inflammatory, vasodilatory, and analgesic properties of leech saliva, concluding that leech therapy is a safe, minimally invasive, and effective treatment option for thrombosed hemorrhoids.(28)
- An experimental study in hyperlipidemic rats showed that leech intervention significantly improved lipid metabolism and liver function. Treatment reduced serum total cholesterol and LDL-C, increased HDL-C, lowered ALT and AST levels, and decreased hepatic lipid accumulation on histological examination. These findings suggest that leech therapy exerts lipid-lowering and hepatoprotective effects and may help attenuate fatty liver changes in hyperlipidemic states (29).

Huqna (Enema)

Enema, known as Huqna or clyster in Unani medicine, is a therapeutic procedure involving the administration of liquid medicinal preparations into the rectum for cleansing, therapeutic, or diagnostic purposes. Traditionally, Huqna has been employed for the evacuation of superfluous and morbid matter from the intestines and is considered an important modality of Ilaj-bil-Tadbeer (regimenal therapy). The term enema originates from the Greek word enienai, meaning “to send in,” reflecting its purpose of introducing medicinal substances into the lower bowel. In both ancient and contemporary medical systems, enemas have been utilized to relieve constipation, facilitate bowel evacuation, administer drugs and nutrients, and support diagnostic procedures such as radiological visualization of the colon. Historical evidence of enema use dates back to ancient Egyptian and Greek civilizations, with notable references by *Hippocrates* and *Galen*. Classical Unani literature attributes the origin of the procedure to observations in nature, describing it as *Amal-e-Tair* (procedure inspired by birds) (30) and later systematized by eminent physicians such as *Ibn Sina* (Avicenna) in *Al-Qanun fi al-Tibb*. Over time, the procedure evolved from rudimentary methods to more refined instruments, including piston syringes and modern disposable micro-enema devices. In Unani medicine, enemas are classified according to their therapeutic objectives, such as *Huqna-e-Muaddil-e-Mizaj*, *Huqna-e-Mushil*, and *Huqna-e-Muhallil* and many others, each designed to restore humoral balance and relieve specific pathological conditions. Thus, enema remains a valuable therapeutic intervention, bridging traditional medical wisdom with contemporary clinical practice.

Key Evidence:

- In this retrospective real-world study involving 1,635 participants from France and Russia with occasional constipation, constipation was found to markedly impair daily activities, emotional well-being, and quality of life, causing discomfort, embarrassment, and anxiety. Across subgroups including women, older adults, and pregnant women, Microlax® microenemas demonstrated high user satisfaction, providing rapid, reliable, and gentle relief. Compared with oral laxatives and rectal suppositories,

microenemas were perceived as easier to use, less painful, and more effective, leading to improved comfort and restoration of a sense of control. Overall, microenemas positively impacted quality of life and were preferred for the management of occasional constipation.(31)

- In this multicenter prospective observational study involving 69 patients with mild-to-moderate ulcerative colitis and bowel urgency, budesonide foam enema led to significant early improvement in bowel urgency and quality of life. Among patients who completed the final evaluation, 58.5% (31/53) achieved resolution of bowel urgency at the end of the 4-week observation period. The rate of bowel urgency resolution increased progressively over time, with a significant difference observed between day 7 and day 0. Improvement in bowel urgency became evident as early as day 5, with statistically significant reduction confirmed by day 12. No adverse events related to budesonide rectal foam were reported. These findings suggest that budesonide foam enema provides safe and

effective early relief of bowel urgency, contributing to improved quality of life in patients with ulcerative colitis (32).

- The systematic review of randomized controlled trials evaluated the effects of sodium butyrate enemas compared with placebo in patients with inflammatory bowel diseases, particularly ulcerative colitis. Across the included trials, sodium butyrate enemas demonstrated a significant reduction in disease activity, with improvement in clinical symptoms, endoscopic scores, and histological inflammatory parameters. Treatment was associated with decreased mucosal inflammation, enhanced epithelial healing, and improved colonic mucosal integrity. Several studies also reported better patient-reported outcomes and tolerability, with minimal adverse effects. Overall, the review supports the therapeutic potential of sodium butyrate enemas as an effective adjunctive treatment for reducing intestinal inflammation and promoting mucosal recovery in inflammatory bowel disease. (33)

TABLE 1: COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF REGIMENAL THERAPIES IN GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDERS

THERAPY	TRADITIONAL RATIONALE	MODERN SCIENTIFIC EXPLANATION	LEVEL OF EVIDENCE (GRADE)
Fasd (Venesection)	Evacuation of excess or morbid blood (Istifragh-e-Dam); relief of Sudda (obstruction); correction of hot temperament of liver (Su'-e-Mizaj Haar)	Reduction of iron overload and oxidative stress; improvement in insulin sensitivity and lipid profile; decreased hepatic inflammation and congestion	Moderate (meta-analysis)
Hammam (Therapeutic Bath /Heat Therapy)	Tahleel-e-Madda (liquefaction of morbid matter); enhancement of circulation; strengthening of digestive faculty (Quwa-e-Hazima)	Improved peripheral and splanchnic blood flow; modulation of gut-brain peptides (motilin, VIP); enhanced bowel motility; metabolic regulation and stress reduction	Low- moderate (small trials)
Ta'liq al-'alaq (Leech therapy)	Local evacuation of Fasad Akhlat; resolution of inflammation (Waram); relief of congestion	Anticoagulant, anti-inflammatory, vasodilatory, and thrombolytic effects of leech saliva; improved	Low (case series)

		microcirculation; reduction of local edema and pain	
Huqna (Medicated enema)	Evacuation of morbid matter from intestines; correction of altered temperament; local resolution of inflammation	Direct rectal drug delivery; stimulation of peristalsis; anti-inflammatory mucosal effects; improvement in bowel urgency, constipation, and mucosal healing	Moderate- High (RCTs)

Comparative Evaluation

When the available evidence is viewed collectively, Unani regimenal therapies demonstrate differing levels of clinical support across gastrointestinal conditions, with their benefits appearing more consistent in selected indications rather than across all disease categories. Fasd (venesection) shows comparatively better evidence in conditions associated with metabolic overload and hepatic congestion. Human studies suggest improvements in laboratory parameters such as iron indices and liver enzymes, which align with the traditional Unani concept of relieving obstruction and excess humoral burden. However, its clinical applicability remains condition-specific and dependent on careful patient selection. Hammam (therapeutic bathing or heat therapy) appears to exert modest yet consistent benefits, particularly in functional gastrointestinal disorders. Patients commonly report improvements in bowel regularity, abdominal discomfort, and overall well-being. From a comparative perspective, its effects may be less immediate than pharmacological agents, but its favorable safety profile and supportive role make it a useful adjunct to standard care. Ta'liq al-'Alaq (Leech Therapy) provides localized benefits, especially in anorectal and inflammatory conditions. Clinical observations indicate reductions in pain, swelling, and local inflammation, which can be explained by the anticoagulant and anti-inflammatory properties of leech saliva. Nonetheless, the current evidence is largely derived from small-scale studies and case series, limiting broad comparative conclusions. Huqna (medicated enema) demonstrates comparatively stronger evidence, particularly in distal bowel disorders. Randomized trials involving rectal formulations such as sodium butyrate enemas have shown meaningful improvements in disease activity

scores, mucosal healing, and inflammatory markers when compared with placebo. These findings provide a clear biomedical parallel to the Unani principle of local evacuation and correction of intestinal temperament. Overall, when compared across effectiveness, safety, cost, and holistic outcomes, Unani regimenal therapies appear most beneficial as complementary approaches rather than replacements for conventional treatment. Their strengths lie in symptom control, improvement of quality of life, and metabolic regulation, while the existing evidence underscores the need for larger, well-designed clinical trials to establish definitive comparative effectiveness.

DISCUSSION

The present review synthesizes available evidence on Unani regimenal therapies in gastrointestinal disorders and interprets their clinical relevance in light of contemporary biomedical understanding. Overall, the findings suggest that these interventions demonstrate context-specific benefits, particularly in functional and inflammatory gastrointestinal conditions, although the quality and quantity of evidence vary considerably across therapies. From an interpretative perspective, Fasd (venesection) appears most relevant in conditions characterized by metabolic overload, hepatic congestion, and low-grade systemic inflammation. Improvements reported in biochemical markers such as liver enzymes and iron indices provide a plausible biomedical explanation for the Unani concept of relieving Sudda (obstruction) and excess humoral accumulation. When compared with modern therapeutic approaches such as phlebotomy in iron overload states, fasd shows conceptual and mechanistic parallels, though it lacks standardized protocols and large comparative

trials. Hammam therapy demonstrates consistent, though modest, benefits in functional gastrointestinal disorders. The observed improvements in bowel regularity, abdominal discomfort, and stress-related symptoms align with modern evidence supporting the role of heat exposure in enhancing circulation, modulating autonomic balance, and improving gut motility. Compared with pharmacological agents, hammam may have a slower onset of action but offers a favorable safety profile and holistic benefits, supporting its role as an adjunct rather than a primary intervention. Leech therapy (Ta'liq al-'Alaq) shows selective effectiveness, particularly in localized anorectal and inflammatory conditions. Its traditional use for evacuating Fasid Akhlat finds partial support in modern studies demonstrating anti-inflammatory, anticoagulant, and microcirculatory effects of leech saliva. However, when compared with standard surgical or pharmacological treatments, the current evidence base remains limited by small sample sizes and methodological heterogeneity, warranting cautious interpretation. Among the reviewed interventions, Huqna (medicated enema) demonstrates comparatively stronger evidence, especially in distal bowel disorders. Randomized controlled trials evaluating rectal sodium butyrate and similar formulations have reported significant improvements in disease activity, endoscopic findings, and histological inflammation when compared with placebo. These findings closely correspond with the Unani principle of local evacuation and temperament correction, highlighting a meaningful convergence between traditional rationale and modern clinical outcomes. In comparison with conventional therapies, Unani regimnal interventions appear most valuable as complementary approaches, contributing to symptom control, quality-of-life improvement, and metabolic modulation rather than replacing standard care.

CONCLUSION

This review synthesizes classical Unani perspectives and contemporary scientific literature to explore the potential relevance of regimnal therapies in gastrointestinal disorders. Although selected studies suggest that interventions such as venesection, therapeutic bathing, leech therapy, and medicated enemas may influence gastrointestinal function and

related metabolic or inflammatory processes, the overall quality of evidence remains limited. Most available data are derived from small clinical studies, observational designs, or indirect mechanistic investigations, restricting the strength of causal inference. At present, these therapies cannot be considered established treatments for gastrointestinal disorders. Any potential benefit should be interpreted cautiously and confined to adjunctive use within appropriately selected patient populations under professional supervision. Among the reviewed interventions, medicated enemas show comparatively stronger support in distal bowel conditions; however, even in this context, evidence is insufficient to support routine clinical recommendation. The observed conceptual overlap between Unani theoretical constructs and modern physiological explanations is hypothesis-generating rather than confirmatory. Substantial gaps remain regarding standardization of interventions, long-term safety, comparative effectiveness, and generalizability.

Future Directions

The heterogeneity of study designs, small participant numbers, and lack of long-term follow-up limit definitive conclusions. Future research should prioritize standardized treatment protocols, well-powered randomized controlled trials, and integration of objective outcome measures to better define their comparative effectiveness and clinical applicability.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

None Declared

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